

INVESTIGATION OF THE PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER / EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATES FABRICATED WITH CO-RFI PROCESS

X.Q. Ma, Y.Z. Gu*, M. Li, Y.X. Li, Z.G. Zhang

School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing 100191, China.

* Corresponding author (benniegu@buaa.edu.cn)

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Abstract

A co-cured process called co-RFI, which combined resin film infusion (RFI) process and prepreg process was adopted to fabricate carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates. The different process procedures, including stacks position of RFI part and prepreg part, temperature dwelling and epoxy tackifier were considered and the effects on the processing quality of co-cured laminates were investigated. Moreover, mode I (G_{IC}) and mode II (G_{IIC}) delamination fracture toughness were measured to compare the interlaminar property of co-RFI laminates with the property of laminates fabricated by sole prepreg and RFI preform, respectively. The results show that all studied laminates have uniform thickness and high fiber compaction degree. However, resin rich and void defects can be observed in co-RFI laminates by certain conditions. The initial G_{IC} and G_{IIC} values of co-RFI laminates locate between those of prepreg laminates and RFI laminates, indicating the interaction of prepreg part and RFI part. Furthermore, a temperature dwell procedure could obviously reduce the resin rich area, increasing the initial G_{IC} and G_{IIC} values of co-RFI laminates and RFI laminates. However, utilization of epoxy tackifier may cause the larger resin rich area for co-RFI laminates. The mechanism of results above is discussed from resin flow and permeation of fiber bed.

1. Introduction

Advanced composites have been widely used in aeronautics and astronautics for many years for the excellent service performances. Traditionally, the prepreg autoclave technique is widely adopted for the accuracy of part dimension and good process quality of composite structure. However, the main barrier to the widespread use of this process is the

high manufacture cost, such as the preparation and storage of prepreg and labor extensive hand layup procedure. Liquid composite molding (LCM) processes, such as resin transfer molding (RTM) and resin film infusion (RFI) process etc., are developed to realize the quick and mass production with low fabrication cost. So considering the two aspects of part quality and low manufacture cost for composite components, combining prepreg process with liquid composite molding process is an important direction for many researchers [1-6]. In these researches, the concept of hybrid process which combined the characters of prepreg and liquid resin infusion process was proposed. Composite structures with good performances and low fabrication cost have been manufactured with this hybrid process. Moreover, the diffusion and compatibility of RTM, VaRI resin with prepreg resin and mechanical performance were investigated in details.

A kind of hybrid process, called co-RFI, combining the prepreg autoclave process and RFI process is presented in this study. The utilization of RFI process in hybrid process exhibits advantages compared with RTM or VARI process [7]: (a) The resin adopted for RFI process has the similar properties with prepreg resin, even some resin could apply for both RFI process and prepreg process, which is favorable of the diffusion and chemical compatibility between the co-cured interlaminar interface; (b) The high fiber content of composite components fabricated by RFI process is close to that of parts by prepreg process, providing the good matching of performance. (c) Changing the long distance resin flow to short thickness direction infusion in the preform reduces the possibility of void and dry spot formation.

A commercial carbon/epoxy resin prepreg and resin film which was the same as prepreg matrix were used to manufacture co-RFI, RFI and prepreg laminates, respectively. The laminate quality and mechanical properties such as G_{IC} and G_{IIC} tests

were conducted to evaluate the difference among three kinds of laminates. Furthermore, the influences of different stacks positions of prepreg part and RFI part, temperature dwelling and epoxy tackifier on the quality and mechanical performances were investigated. The research results show that co-RFI technique exhibits good process feasibility and laminate quality with low manufacture cost.

2. Experiment

2.1 Materials

In this experiment, the epoxy resin film with areal density of 200g/m^2 was provided by Advanced Composites Group Co., Ltd. (ACG) which was the same as matrix resin of MTM44-1 prepreg (supplied by ACG). T700SC carbon fiber unidirectional fabric (CFW-200, supplied by Jiangsu Tianniao High Technology Co. Ltd.) and MTM44-1 unidirectional epoxy prepreg with areal density of 134g/m^2 were adopted for RFI and prepreg process, respectively. Moreover, an epoxy tackifier used to ensure the dimension and shape of fabric was produced by Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials (BIAM).

2.2 Laminates manufacture

In order to evaluate the quality and mechanical properties of co-RFI laminates with sole RFI and prepreg laminates. Laminates were manufactured by autoclave prepreg process, RFI process and co-RFI process, respectively.

2.2.1 Prepreg autoclave process

Unidirectional carbon /epoxy prepreg was cut into $300\text{mm}\times 200\text{mm}$ size and 32 layers were located on the steel plate according to 0° direction. A Teflon film was placed in the mid-plane of prepreg stacks as a creating crack for G_{IC} and G_{IIC} tests. The cure cycle of prepreg laminates was as follows: The autoclave raised temperature from ambient to 180°C at $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and held at 180°C for two hours. 0.4MPa external pressure and -0.1MPa vacuum were applied through the cure cycle.

2.2.2 RFI process

For 4mm-thickness laminates with 60% fiber volume fraction, 20 layers of unidirectional carbon fiber fabric and 9 layers of resin film could be used [8]. Bagging arrangement for RFI process was presented in Fig. 1. Resin film and fiber fabric were placed on the steel plate successively. A Teflon sheet was laid between the 10th and 11th layers as a pre-crack. The whole stacks were covered with

release film and breather, surrounded by dam, and finally sealed in vacuum bag.

1-Steel plate 2-Breather 3- Release ply 4-Dam 5- Resin film 6- Teflon film 7- Fiber perform 8- Release film 9- Vacuum valve 10- Sealant tap 11- Vacuum bag

Fig. 1 Schematic of the bagging procedure in RFI process

2.2.3 Co-RFI process

The 4mm-thickness co-RFI laminate was fabricated by RFI part (including 10 layers of fabric and 5 layers of resin film) and prepreg part (containing 16 layers of MTM44-1 prepreg layers). The position effect of RFI and prepreg stacks was considered as shown in Fig. 2. The RFI stacks was located under the prepreg stacks, called prepreg/RFI stacks as illustrated in Fig. 2(a). Exchanging the positions of prepreg stacks and RFI stacks was named as RFI/prepreg stacks in Fig. 2(b). The bagging arrangement was the same as RFI process.

1-Teflon film 2-Resin film 3-Fiber fabric 4-Prepreg stacks

Fig. 2. Schematic of two kinds of stacks positions: (a) prepreg/RFI stacks (b) RFI/prepreg stacks.

2.3 Laminate process procedures

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Three kinds of process procedures were designed to discuss the influences of process procedures on RFI and co-RFI process as follows:

(A) Heat from room temperature (about 25 °C) at the rate of 2 °C/min to 180 °C, maintained at 180 °C for 2 hours, cooled down at 2 °C/min to 65 °C as the manufacturer recommended.

(B) Heat from room temperature (about 25 °C) at the rate of 2 °C/min to 130 °C, maintained at 130 °C for 30min and then increased to 180 °C at 2 °C/min, followed by a 2 hours stage at 180 °C, finally cooled down as mentioned in process A.

(C) The 8% weight percent tackifier was grinded into small powdery particles and uniformly dispersed on fiber fabric. Then perform was treated at 80 °C for 5min in co-RFI process. The same temperature cycle was applied as described in process B.

The 0.4MPa external pressure and -0.1MPa vacuum were applied through the cure cycle for three process procedures above.

2.4 Test

2.4.1 Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness

Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness test (G_{IC}) was carried out by double cantilever beam (DCB) mode according to ASTM D5528. The profile of load and crack length was plotted and G_{IC} was calculated by the following equation:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + |\Delta|)} \quad (1)$$

Where P is the load (N), δ is the displacement (mm), b is the specimen width (mm), a is the delamination length (mm), Δ is the horizontal axis intercept from a-C^{1/3} curve. The compliance, C, is the ratio of the load point displacement to the applied load, δ/P .

The critical G_{IC} value was obtained as the average of the G_{IC} values of the 50mm delamination length while the propagation value of G_I was calculated from the stable crack values at the delamination length about 70-90mm for each specimen group.

2.4.2 Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness

End-notch flexure test for G_{IIC} was conducted by HB 7403-96. The G_{IIC} value was obtained on the basis of following equation:

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{9P\delta a^2}{2b(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \times 10^3 \quad (2)$$

Where P is the load (N), δ is the displacement according to load (mm), a is the effective

delamination length (mm), b is the specimen width (mm), L is the half-span length (mm)

The peak load at first time and load at deviation point in the second reloading curves were used to calculate for initial and propagation G_{IIC} values, respectively.

2.4.3 Other property tests

Average thickness was measured at five positions for each group of laminates as shown in Fig. 3. The fiber volume fraction of different laminates was obtained according to the fiber fabric areal density and average thickness of laminates [8].

Fig. 3. Regions of cured laminates for thickness measurement

The cured laminates were cut into small pieces and the cross sections of samples were wet ground with successively finer silicon carbide paper and wet polished with chromium oxide. The polished sections were observed by Olympus BX51M optical microscope to investigate the defects formed during different processes.

The crack surfaces of specimens after G_{IC} test were observed by Aplo 300 Field Emission SEM for analyzing the interfacial adhesion between fiber and resin.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Process quality of different laminates

The defects, such as voids, resin rich and delamination etc., have significant influence on the performances of composite components [9, 10]. The process quality of laminates fabricated by process A, B and C was evaluated through thickness and fiber volume fraction. The thickness of different laminates was shown in Table 1. There is slightly difference of thickness by process A and process B. But the thickness of laminates for process C is larger than

that of laminates by process A due to the application of epoxy tackifier. Compared with prepreg and RFI laminates, the co-RFI laminates exhibit a little higher thickness. In general, all the laminates have uniformly thickness without obvious difference.

Table 1. Thickness of different laminates

	Thickness/mm		
	Process A	Process B	Process C
RFI laminate	3.97±0.02	3.91±0.04	4.08±0.03
RFI/Prepreg laminate	4.04±0.02	4.02±0.05	4.15±0.04
Prepreg/RFI laminate	4.11±0.02	4.09±0.03	4.17±0.04
Prepreg laminate	3.99±0.02	---	---

Table 2 illustrates the fiber volume fraction of different laminates. From the aspect of different process procedures, laminates by process B present the highest fiber volume fraction values, follows by laminates by process A. Minimum fiber content belongs to laminates by process C in each process group, attributing to the utilization of tackifier. From the process aspect, co-RFI laminates show mediate fiber volume fraction among prepreg, RFI and co-RFI laminates.

Table 2. Fiber volume fraction of different laminates

	Fiber volume fraction /%		
	Process A	Process B	Process C
RFI laminate	59.1±0.2	60.1±0.3	57.5±0.2
RFI/Prepreg laminate	58.7±0.1	59.0±0.4	57.1±0.3
Prepreg/RFI laminate	57.7±0.3	58.0	56.9
Prepreg laminate	60.1±0.2	---	---

The micrographs of RFI laminates fabricated by process A, B, C and prepreg laminates by process A are shown in Fig. 4. Compared with the high and uniform fiber compaction of prepreg laminates, resin rich area and small void defect exist in RFI laminates by process A and B. It is due to the large fiber tows and stitched line along width direction of RFI preform and slightly high viscosity of resin film during resin infusion. A 30minites temperature dwelling in process B gives more opportunity for sufficient resin flow and fabric impregnation, resulting in the decrease of resin rich region in laminates by process B as presented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Micrographs of RFI laminates cured by (a) process A (b) process B (c) process C and prepreg laminate by (d) process A

Fig. 5. Micrographs of RFI/prepreg laminates cured by (a) process A (b) process B (c) process C and prepreg /RFI laminates by (d) process A (e) process B (f) process C

The investigation of process quality focused on RFI/prepreg and prepreg/RFI laminates is presented in Fig. 5. Compared with RFI/prepreg laminates, larger resin rich region occurs in RFI part and the co-cured interlaminar interface for the prepreg/RFI

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laminates fabricated by process A and process B. Furthermore, void defects could be found in prepreg/RFI laminates which indicates the negative effects of prepreg/RFI stacks on resin flow and gas elimination.

Considering all the laminates fabricated by process C, there is similar process quality except larger resin redundant area compared with laminates by process A and process B. The low viscosity (about 5 Pa·s) from 130 to 230 °C of tackifier and modest compatibility between tackifier and RFI resin ensure the good flow and sufficient impregnation of fabric. However, utilization of tackifier also increases the risk of resin rich phenomenon at the same time.

3.2 Characterization of co-cured interface

Co-cured interface is special and crucial contact region for co-RFI technique. G_{IC} and G_{IIC} tests are used to evaluate the properties of co-RFI laminates chosen from RFI/prepreg laminates by process A.

Fig. 6. The critical G_{IC} values of different laminates by process A

The critical G_{IC} values of different laminates fabricated by process A are presented in Fig. 6. The prepreg laminates gives maximum value about $222 J \cdot m^{-2}$, follows by the similar values of $192 J \cdot m^{-2}$ and $190 J \cdot m^{-2}$ for RFI/prepreg and prepreg/RFI laminates, respectively. The smallest critical G_{IC} value belongs to RFI laminates. The maximum critical G_{IC} values results from the high fiber compaction degree laminates with little defects such as resin rich and void. For RFI laminates, the existing resin rich and void defects are unfavorable to the performance of interlaminar interface, leading to a smallest critical G_{IC} value. The mediate values for co-RFI laminates demonstrate the mutual influence of RFI part and prepreg part.

Mode I delamination resistance curves (R-curve) of laminates above are shown in Fig. 7. There are two different crack propagation patterns in Fig. 7, as follows: (a) The crack for prepreg laminates always runs along the mid-plane with a stable and continuous pattern, which presents a smooth and flat R-curve. (b) For the other three kinds of laminates, the crack occurs in the mid-plane in the beginning, but as the crack continues, the propagation direction may deviate from center line, go to neighbor layer and even multiple crack tips extend simultaneously. The deflection of crack and fiber bridge effect lead larger fracture area and high driving force, resulting in higher propagation G_{IC} values compared with that of prepreg laminates [11-13].

Fig. 7. Mode I delamination resistance curves (R-curves) of laminates by process A

The graphs of SEM fracture morphology at delamination region for G_{IC} specimens are shown in Fig. 8. The fibers are regular and orderly arrangement with little resin on the surface for prepreg laminates. In contrast, much resin is adhered to the fibers and the some fibers are pulled out, indicating the strong effect of fiber bridge effects during crack propagation for the other three kinds laminates. The different stacks positions for co-RFI laminates have the similar fracture surface from SEM graphs. However, rougher fiber surface with resin adhesion compared with fracture morphology for sole prepreg laminates. Moreover, the groove left by fibers and the rough resin fracture section could be clearly observed at surface for RFI part of co-RFI laminates. The huge difference of fracture morphology of RFI and prepreg laminates indicates the influence of different kinds of carbon fiber reinforcement in RFI part and prepreg part, respectively.

Fig. 8. Fracture morphology at delamination area of G_{IC} specimens by process A (a) prepreg laminate (b) RFI laminate (c) prepreg layer of RFI/prepreg laminate (d) RFI layer of RFI/prepreg laminate (e) prepreg layer of prepreg/RFI laminate (f) RFI layer of prepreg/RFI laminate

Fig. 9. The initial G_{IIc} values of different laminates fabricated by process A

From Fig. 9, prepreg laminates and RFI laminates occupy the highest and smallest initial G_{IIc} value, about $2763 \text{ J}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ and $548 \text{ J}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$, respectively. The initial G_{IIc} values for co-RFI laminates locate between those of prepreg laminates and RFI laminates, which are $1415 \text{ J}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ and $1155 \text{ J}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ for RFI/prepreg and prepreg/RFI laminates, respectively. In contrast to prepreg laminates, the poor

compaction and resin rich area existing in RFI laminates result in low values, while the mediate values for co-RFI laminates are dependent on both RFI part and prepreg part.

3.3 Influence of process procedures on the interlaminar performances

The process procedures such as cure cycle and bagging arrangement have important influence on defects forming and performances of composite components. As to co-RFI process, it is necessary to investigate the effects of the temperature dwelling and utilization of tackifier on the co-RFI laminates. The process quality of co-RFI laminates has been discussed in section 3.1. The results of G_{IC} and G_{IIC} tests for co-RFI laminates by process A, B and C are illustrated in this section.

3.3.1 Effects of temperature dwelling

The critical G_{IC} values for laminates by process A and B are shown in Fig. 10. The critical G_{IC} values of co-RFI and RFI laminates by process B are higher than values of laminates by process A for each group. The fracture surface morphology of laminates for process B is observed by SEM as listed in Fig. 11. Compared with the surface morphology of laminates by process A, more resin is adhered with fibers and river-like crack texture appears in resin damage region, indicating in strong fiber-resin interfacial performance and better mechanical property of co-cured interface.

Fig. 10. The critical G_{IC} values of laminates by process A and process B

The G_{IIC} results for laminates by process B are summarized in Fig. 12. Temperature dwelling in cured cycle obviously improves the initial G_{IIC} values of the RFI and prepreg/RFI laminates, but

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have no significant increase for RFI/prepreg laminates.

In general, the 130 °C temperature dwelling offers enough time for sufficient resin flow, fiber impregnation and gas elimination.

Fig. 11. Fracture morphology at delamination area of G_{IC} specimens by process B (a) prepreg layer of co-RFI laminate (b) RFI layer of co-RFI laminate (c) RFI laminate

Fig. 12. The initial G_{IC} values of laminates by process A and process B

3.3.2 Effects of tackifier

Tackifier plays an important role on keeping the dimension and shape of fiber perform. The properties of tackifier during cure cycle and the resin compatibility between tackifier and RFI resin may influence the process quality and final performance of composite components [14-18]. The effect of tackifier on co-RFI laminates is discussed through laminates by process B and C.

The critical G_{IC} values and the corresponding propagation fracture surface morphology of G_{IC}

specimens by process B and process C are presented in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14, respectively. The results show that tackifier increase the critical G_{IC} values for RFI laminates and have negligible influence on prepreg/RFI laminates. However, RFI/prepreg laminates suffer an 18.6% decrease on critical G_{IC} values. Two main factors are considered to explain the results: (a) The tackifier used in this research is a kind of tough epoxy resin with suitable viscosity during resin flow and diffusion in cure cycle. The toughness effect shows improvement in G_{IC} values. (b) The utilization of tackifier increases the possibility of forming resin rich region in co-cured interface, which present negative effect on critical G_{IC} values. Therefore the critical G_{IC} values exhibit different tendency for the mutual influences of two factors above.

Fig. 13. The critical G_{IC} values of laminates by process B and process C

Fig. 14. Fracture morphology at delamination area of laminates by process C (a) prepreg layer of co-RFI laminate (b) RFI layer of co-RFI laminate (c) RFI laminate

As shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 14, there is little difference for fiber-resin adhesion between laminates fabricated by process B and C. Tackifier has negligible influence on the resin diffusion in fiber fabric as certified from fracture propagation morphology.

The initial G_{IIC} values for different laminates by process B and C are listed in Fig. 15. For the laminates fabricated with tackifier, the initial G_{IIC} values of RFI and RFI/prepreg laminates increase, while values of prepreg/RFI laminates suffer decrease, which are ascribed to resin redundant caused by tackifier as well as the hindered effect of top prepreg stacks on resin flow in preform.

Fig. 15. The initial G_{IIC} values of laminates by process B and process C

4. Conclusion

A new hybrid process which combined prepreg autoclave process and RFI process was introduced in this article. The optical micrographs of different laminates present that resin rich region and void defects appear in RFI part and the co-cured interface of co-RFI laminates, especially for prepreg/RFI laminates. The results of G_{IC} and G_{IIC} tests show mediate critical G_{IC} values and initial G_{IIC} values for co-RFI laminates compared with those of prepreg laminates and RFI laminates. The propagation G_{IC} values for RFI and co-RFI laminates are similar but give higher values than those of prepreg laminates due to involvement of fiber bridge and deflection of delamination. Furthermore, the process procedures play significant influences on the quality and performance of laminates. Firstly, for different stacks positions, the RFI/prepreg position is favor of gas elimination, resin flow and fiber impregnation, resulting in better laminate quality with low void content and resin rich area. Secondly, Positive

effects of temperature dwelling could be found from the improvement of critical G_{IC} and initial G_{IIC} values. Thirdly, utilization of tackifier in co-RFI process could increase the possibility of resin redundant and reduce the performances of co-cured interface in co-RFI laminates. In summary, it is proved that selecting suitable procedures and accurately controlling process parameters in cure cycle, co-RFI technique is a feasible process for composite manufacture with low fabricated cost in future.

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